

IMPLEMENTATION OF THE ZERO-PLASTIC PROJECTS AMONG STAKEHOLDERS

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IMPLEMENTATION OF THE ZERO-PLASTIC PROJECTS AMONG STAKEHOLDERS

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ABSTRACT

This study follows the descriptive type of research which aims to determine the level of awareness and involvement of stakeholders in the implementation of the zero-plastic projects in Hilongos National Vocational School. There were 267 respondents which were composed of 96 JHS students, 56 teachers, 11 administrators, 96 JHS parents and 8 barangay officials for the academic year 2021-2022. A survey questionnaire was used to gather the responses of the different stakeholders. The study revealed that the stakeholders were moderately aware on the zero-plastic projects, claimed to be involved and the projects itself were implemented in the school level. Stakeholder's awareness and involvement have a significant relationship on the level of implementation of the zero-plastic projects. This means that the level of awareness and involvement is directly influenced by the level of implementation of the projects. Scarcity of funds to purchase materials needed for the zero-plastic project activity, limited time allocation for zero-plastic project activities and conflict of schedules between important task and zero-plastic project activities are the top 3 problems faced by the stakeholders in the implementation of the zero-plastic projects. In response to the problems faced by the respondents, a sustainable program on school's zero-plastic projects is proposed.

Keywords: *Stakeholders, awareness, involvement, implementation of zero-plastic projects*

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INTRODUCTION

Plastic material offers numerous properties such as lightweight, resilience, resistance to corrosion, color, transparency, and ease of processing, which makes them superior over other materials in many applications. Additionally, versatility, low cost, and abundance of plastic materials have encouraged application in products requiring multipurpose performance criteria on a daily basis. According to Shrivastava (2018), single product can necessitate a combination of properties to satisfy all of its requirements. However, plastic pollution is a pervasive and growing problem. It is globally existing. It is found throughout the oceans, in lakes and rivers, in soils and sediments, in the atmosphere, and in animal biomass. Lau (2020) states that a sharp rise in single-use plastic consumption and an expanding “throw-away” culture have exacerbated the problem.

Waste management systems do not have sufficient capacity at the global level to safely dispose of or recycle waste plastic resulting in an inevitable increase in plastic pollution into the environment. Previous studies estimated that 8 million metric tons (Mt) of macroplastic and 1.5 Mt of primary microplastic enter the ocean annually. Comparable estimates for terrestrial plastic pollution have yet to be quantified. If plastic production and waste generation continue to grow at current rates, the annual mass of mismanaged waste has been projected to more than double by 2050 and the cumulative mass of ocean plastic could increase by an order of magnitude from 2010 levels by 2025. Despite the magnitude of these flows, the efficacy and economic costs of solutions proposed to solve the plastic waste problem—the uncontrolled release of plastic waste into the environment resulting from ineffective management—remain unknown. (Lau, et.al, 2020).

The concerned lawmakers of the Philippines implemented existing laws and policies to probably solve the problem. Two of which are the Republic Act No. 9003 Ecological Solid Waste Management Act of 2000 and Republic Act No. 9512, the National Environmental Awareness and Education Act of 2008. As one of the agencies of the government, the Department of Education fully supports these republic acts thus, implementing several DepEd Orders. In view of the pressing global concerns and issues on the environment, the Department of Education (DepEd) urges all public and private schools to lead the role on environmental awareness by enhancing environmental education and by pursuing effective school-based activities that seek to preserve and protect the environment. This is in pursuant to Republic Act (R.A.) No. 9512, entitled “An Act to Promote Environmental Education and for Other Purposes”. With this, the Department of Education established the Youth for Environment in School Organizations (YES- O) pursuant to DepEd Order No. 72, s. 2003 in all public and private elementary (Grades IV-VI) and secondary schools. Through DepEd Order No. 93, s. 2011, it mandated programs, projects and activities, various forms and target pertinent to the Youth for Environment in Schools (YES) Program. As part of the Department of Education and as a duly registered organization of the Division of Leyte, the HNVS Youth for Environment in Schools Organization is up to the challenge. Organization is up to the challenge.

The different environmental activities mandated to the YES-O, it can be considered as a holistic approach in promoting environmental care and sustainable development, and proven to be more relevant today. From its establishment in 2003, it has been a frontrunner in

empowering the youth to protect and care for the natural environment by providing relevant and meaningful activities (Perez & Bua, 2019). Accordingly, Perez and Bua (2019) reported that local educational leaders emphasized that the enrichment of learnings about the environment can be done through co-curricular activities of environmental youth organizations like YES-O. One of which is the plastic free environment. Waste is commonly assumed to be a valueless and unavoidable by-product that is created at the end of a product's life phase. The zero-waste approach directly challenges this common assumption and finds the ways to reuse the so-called "waste" by-products. The toxic waste approach states that merely minimizing plastic waste impacts is not enough. Rather, in this approach all plastic waste is a poison that cannot be tolerated (Zaman & Newman, 2021).

Schools play a vital role in supporting the people's constitutional rights to life and property by capacitating them for disaster risk reduction and climate change adaptation (DRR-CCA). Consequently, several environmental policies were legislated, and for the past years, better environmental education expected to uplift the awareness and achievement of people especially students were recommended and promoted (Perez & Bua, 2019). The school implements such programs stipulated in the DepEd Order No. 93, s. 2011. Hilongos National Vocational School implemented the zero-plastic projects for four years now. However, due to the temporary closure of schools in the year 2020, the stakeholders' awareness about the program was affected. In addition, its implementation was quite a challenge. It has been observed that this school is still facing problems on proper waste disposal and solid waste management. Unlabeled trash bins from classrooms to the school as a whole, mis cooperation among students, teachers, and vendors, and insufficiency of compost pits were several hindrances for these programs to be in full swing. With this, the researcher aims to provide more solutions to these impending problems.

The zero-plastic projects have been implemented in Hilongos National Vocational School since the year 2018, the same year when the researcher started being the adviser of the Youth for Environment in Schools Organization of the said school.

This study was conducted to assess the implementation level of the zero-plastic project. The findings of this study would guide the school administrator and maybe later on the Local Government Unit in promoting a plastic-free environment. This would also serve as a strengthening measure in designing school-based zero-plastic activities for an eco-friendly school and a sustainable program for all the stakeholders.

The study determined the implementation level of the zero-plastic projects among stakeholders of the Hilongos National Vocational School. Specifically, this study assessed the stakeholders' level of awareness on school's zero-plastic projects, the stakeholders' level of involvement on the implementation of school's zero-plastic projects, the level of implementation of school's zero-plastic projects, the significant relationship among the stakeholders' level of awareness, level of involvement and implementation on school's zero plastic projects, the problems faced by the stakeholders in the implementation of the zero-plastic projects and the proposed sustainable program based from the output of the study.

METHODOLOGY

The target respondents of this study were the stakeholders in Hilongos National Vocational School, R.V. Fulache St. Barangay Central Hilongos, Leyte. They comprised the students, teachers, administrators as the internal stakeholders and the parents and barangay officials as the external stakeholders. The researcher used Slovin's Formula in determining the sample size of the students, teachers, and parents. The school administrators and barangay officials were completely enumerated. Table I presents the distribution and total number of respondents.

The Sample and Locale of the Study

Since Covid-19 cases are still rising presently, the researcher reduced the population size in order to conform the safety protocol. From the original sample size of 875, it was reduced to 267 respondents through increasing the marginal error from 0.05 to 0.10 in computing the sample size using the Slovin's formula. The sample size is 267 out of the total population of 5575.

For the students, simple stratified sampling was used where every grade level from the junior high school is represented. Same it goes for the sample size of the parents where it was estimated that every student had their corresponding parent or guardian that would also answer their separate survey questionnaire. This was to ensure that the sample size is reliable and representative. Administrators and barangay officials were determined through complete enumeration.

Table 1. Distribution of Respondents

Stakeholders	Population (N)	Sample Size (n)	Percentage of Participants (%)
JHS Students	2713	96	36
JHS Teachers	130	56	21
Administrators	11	11	4
JHS Parents	2713	96	36
Brgy. Officials	8	8	3
Total	5575	267	100

Instrumentation

The study used a survey questionnaire to gather the necessary data. Indicators from Parts I, II and III were modified by the researcher based from mandated programs, projects and activities pertinent to the Youth for Environment in Schools (YES) program. The indicators of the Part IV were modified by the researcher from the study of R.W. Nderitu (2011) which focuses on roles of school-based clubs in addressing environmental threats. The tool contains four major parts.

Gathering of Data

The researcher secured permission from the Dean of the Graduate School and then to the Principal of the school where the researcher is working. Upon approval, the researcher sent an informatory letter to all the respondents of the study. The letter for the students was addressed to the parents asking consent for their child and themselves to participate in the conduct of the study.

A survey questionnaire was used in this study. It has four parts to be filled in by the respondents. Part I assessed the stakeholder's awareness on school's zero plastic project. This measured their degree of knowledge about the presence of the different school's zero-plastic project initiatives. In this part, the respondents just checked the zero-plastic projects which they think exist in the school. This part of the tool had 20 indicators. Part II assessed stakeholders' level of involvement on the school's zero-plastic project. The respondents may be extremely involved, involved, moderately involved, slightly involved or not involved at all. Still, this had 20 indicators.

Part III assessed the program's level of implementation within the school premises. The respondents in the mentioned parts rated the following indicators according to the degree of their agreement or disagreement using a scale of 1-5, where 5 is the highest and 1 is the lowest. It may be extremely implemented, implemented, moderately implemented, slightly implemented or not implemented. This part had 20 indicators all in all. Part IV contained the possible problems faced by the stakeholders in the implementation of the school's zero-plastic projects. Respondents just put a check mark on the indicator which they encountered in the implementation of the zero-plastic projects. Part IV had 14 indicators in totality.

Data Analysis

Responses to the stakeholders' awareness on the zero-plastic projects in the school were analyzed using descriptive statistics such as frequency, percentage and rank. The frequency and percentage of responses for each item / project was determined by tallying and counting the responses falling under each category. The number of check marks (/) among the twenty indicators is the score of the respondents for their awareness on the zero-plastic projects.

The weighted mean was used in analyzing the level of involvement of stakeholders on the implementation of the school's zero-plastic project. It was interpreted using the scale below to determine the extent as to how involved they were in the zero-plastic projects.

Table 2. Awareness on the Zero-Plastic Project

WEIGHTED MEAN	LEVEL OF INVOLVEMENT	INTERPRETATION
4.50 to 5.00	Extremely Involved	The stakeholder is highly involved on the implementation of the school's zero-plastic project
3.50 to 4.49	Involved	The stakeholder is acceptably involved on the implementation of the school's zero-plastic project
2.50 to 3.49	Moderately Involved	The stakeholder is moderately involved on the implementation of the school's zero-plastic project
1.50 to 2.49	Slightly Involved	The stakeholder is slightly involved on the implementation of the school's zero-plastic project
1.00 to 1.49	Not Involved	The stakeholder is completely not involved on the implementation of the school's zero-plastic project

The weighted mean was utilized to determine the level of implementation of the school's zero-plastic project. The scale to which the results were interpreted was also written below.

Table 3. Level of Implementation of the School's Zero-Plastic Project

WEIGHTED MEAN	LEVEL OF IMPLEMENTATION	REPRESENTATION
4.50 to 5.00	Extremely Implemented	The zero-plastic project is highly implemented in the school level
3.50 to 4.49	Implemented	The zero-plastic project is acceptably implemented in the school level
2.50 to 3.49	Moderately Implemented	The zero-plastic project is moderately implemented in the school level
1.50 to 2.49	Slightly Implemented	The zero-plastic project is slightly implemented in the school level
1.00 to 1.49	Not Implemented	The zero-plastic project is completely not implemented in the school level

In determining the significance of relationship among the stakeholders' level of awareness, level of involvement and the school's level of implementation of the zero-plastic project, Chi- square test was used

The responses to the presence of possible problems faced by the stakeholders was analyzed using descriptive statistics such as frequency, percentage and rank. Frequency was determined by tallying and counting of responses falling under each category.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This part comprehensively discusses, analyzes and interprets the data obtained which were treated accordingly through the use of statistical tools.

Figure 1. Stakeholders' Level of Awareness on School's Zero-Plastic Projects

The data show that the Hilongos National Vocational School has implemented the different zero-plastic projects which were mandated by the Youth for Environment in Schools Organization. By averaging the number of responses, it resulted to 188 as the average number of responses which is equivalent to 71% of the whole respondents. This figure shows that generally, the stakeholders were moderately aware of the zero-plastic projects existing in the school. This is due to the fact that the face-to-face classes were stopped for two years so some projects were not that familiar to the internal and most especially the external stakeholders who are not present in the school all the time. Since the average number of responses was derived, the number of responses to the projects which stakeholders were not that aware of affected the average value for the level of awareness as a whole. However, based on the rank, there are (3) top most projects that respondents are most aware of. These are the Properly labeled trash bins (90%), School clean-up activities / ground cleaning (88%) and Practice reduce, reuse, recycle (86%). Results show that properly labeled trash bins got the highest percentage among the

school's zero-plastic projects (90%). This is evidenced by the data that out of 267 stakeholders, 241 stakeholders have responded to this indicator. General waste signs and recycling bin stickers encourage people to recycle their waste in society. By providing people with an easy method of categorizing waste, items could be recycled and disposed accordingly. Waste management is an area that is still in development with advances still to be made, but having clearly labelled bins with recycling bin labels is one way to encourage people to play one's part in the reduction of harmful waste. Best (2017) emphasized that general waste signs should be distinguished from one another by color and clear graphics logos which are easy to comprehend. This should help to maximize the amount of waste recycled in society and reduce what is sent to landfill sites. This concur on the result since labeled trash bins (biodegradable, non-biodegradable and recyclable) are found inside and outside every classroom and within the school premises.

Generally, the results show that Hilongos National Vocational School have practiced the different zero-plastic projects with varying ranks of stakeholders' awareness. The varying level of awareness is affected by the COVID-19 restrictions and the temporary stoppage of the face-to-face classes among schools.

Figure 2. Stakeholders' Level of Involvement on School's Zero-Plastic Projects

Results revealed that the overall weighted mean of the indicators for the stakeholders' level of involvement on school zero-plastic projects is 3.95. Generally, the stakeholders in Hilongos National Vocational School which comprise the students, teachers, administrators, parents and barangay officials were highly involved on the different school's zero-plastic projects.

Based on the rank of the weighted mean, there are top three zero-plastic projects which stakeholders involved themselves into. These are following the labeled trash bins (4.50), bringing and using their own tumbler in school, at home and in the workplace (4.48) and using water jug/dispenser at school and at home (4.42).

The result revealed that stakeholders are extremely involved in following the labeled trash bins. This shows that most of the stakeholders are throwing their wastes on the respective trash bins allocated for it. This is due to the fact that of a very visible and well-labeled trash bins inside the classrooms and along the hallways of the school are in place. The presence is a big factor of stakeholders' involvement. As a result, trashes are segregated properly. This is also due to the mechanism of the Youth for Environment in Schools Organization wherein each classroom is checked and monitored if they follow the mandate of the zero-plastic projects. Waste segregation is defined as the process of identifying, classifying, dividing and sorting of garbage and waste products in an effort to reduce, reuse and recycle materials.

Figure 3. Level of Implementation on School's Zero-Plastic Projects

Data shows that Hilongos National Vocational School implemented the zero-plastic projects in the school level with an overall weighted mean of 4.13 (refer to Appendix E). This explains that the school really implemented the mandates by the YES-O which aims for a zero-plastic environment.

Based on the graph that shows the different indicators, it can be said that the most implemented zero-plastic project is the Labeled trash bins in each classroom and offices with a weighted mean of 4.52. This figure presents the fact that it is extremely implemented all throughout the vicinity of the campus. It is directly interrelated with the top answer for the level of awareness and involvement of the stakeholders. Since the stakeholders are extremely aware (90%) and extremely involved (4.5 weighted mean), they tend to extremely implement the said zero-plastic project inside their classrooms, offices and in their homes as well. The students are

the major internal stakeholders, they composed most of the respondents in this study while the parents are the external stakeholders. With this, Herdiansyah (2021) states that when students learn about waste management and its implementation, just like the labeled trash bins, they can implement the management activities that have been carried out in schools in their home. With these activities, students will be able to influence the behavior of their parents, and this is a school education activity that can affect the community environment indirectly. Children can change their parents' lifestyle regarding the environment. Education in schools can play a role in increasing public participation in environmental management.

Table 4. Significant Relationship Among the Stakeholders' Level of Awareness, Implementation, and Involvement on School's Zero Plastic Projects

School Zero-Plastic Projects		Chi-Square Test			Correlation		Description
		Computed Value	Df	p-value	Coefficient	p-value	
Stakeholders Level of Implementation	Level of Awareness	8.847 ^{ns}	8	.355	.169**	.006	Highly Significant
	Level of Involvement	83.461**	4	.000	.495**	.000	Highly Significant

Based on the result, the computed Chi-Square value between the level of implementation and level of awareness is not significant since p-value (.355) is greater than .05. The correlation coefficient between the Level of implementation and level of awareness is highly significant since p-value (.006) is less than .01. There is a low positive correlation (.169) but significant relationship between level of awareness and level of implementation. This means that those who responded high (level) for awareness, responded high (level) in the implementation. Also, those who responded low (level) for awareness, responded low (level) in the implementation.

There is a significant relationship between the level of implementation and level of involvement as shown in a highly significant Chi-Square and Correlation values. Actual number of stakeholders in the Level 3 Involvement who are in the Level 3 Implementation (12) is significantly higher than what is expected (2.6). This means that those who were moderately involved tend to moderately implement the school's zero plastic projects. Actual number of stakeholders in the Level 4 Involvement who are in the Level 4 Implementation (47) is significantly higher than what is expected (28.9). This means that those who were highly involved tend to highly implement the school's zero plastic projects. Actual number of stakeholders in the Level 5 Involvement who are in the Level 5 Implementation (93) is significantly higher than what is expected (66.8). This means that those who were extremely involved tend to extremely implement the school's zero plastic projects.

The correlation coefficient between the Level of implementation and level of involvement is highly significant since p-value (.000) is less than .01. There is a significant

moderate positive relationship (.495) between the level of involvement and level of implementation. This means that those who responded high (level) for involvement, responded high (level) in the implementation. Also, those who responded low (level) for involvement, responded low (level) in the implementation.

Overall, the findings indicate and show that the level of awareness and involvement of the stakeholders of Hilongos National Vocational School directly affect how it is implemented having a probability level or p-value $.006 < .01$ and $.000 < .01$ respectively which means it is significant. The results imply that the more aware and involve the stakeholders are, the more they implement the zero plastic projects. Khatibi (2021) notes that the public’s awareness and knowledge can contribute to their engagement in decision-making and increased engagement in turn can influence the community’s level of awareness and knowledge. In addition, Wibeck (2015) reiterates that there is a positive relationship between knowledge and engagement. The research concludes that although a lack of knowledge is an important barrier to active engagement, knowledge and awareness without engagement are not sufficient for changing people’s behavior and lifestyle. Moreover, it illustrates that public participation, and particularly active participation in environmental matters can significantly contribute to gaining knowledge and awareness. Together, public awareness, knowledge, and participation can drive changes in public behavior and actions regarding a project implementation.

Figure 4. Problems Faced by the Stakeholders in the Implementation of the Zero-Plastic Projects

Respondents revealed that the top three (3) problems that they faced were: not enough funds to purchase materials needed for the zero-plastic project activity (61%), limited time allocation for zero-plastic project activities (55%) and conflict of schedule between important task and zero-plastic project activities (53%).

Not enough funds to purchase materials needed for the zero-plastic project activity is the major problem faced by stakeholders since some of the activities need financial support for it to be successful. The budget for the eco-friendly school reflected in the Annual Implementation Plan is not given to the organization. Instead, it is redirected to other operating

expenses of the school. Some students do not have resources to buy the required tumbler and the organization cannot fully provide this to all the students who do not have this tumbler. As a result, these students tend to buy drinks in plastic containers or sachets. Fare and snacks for the activity participants is also one factor that affects why some of the zero-plastic projects are not that implemented regularly. Cleaning tools and rainwater collectors were also not purchased due to scarcity of funds. The fund needed for the establishment of a compost pit for the mega school was also not possible these days so at present the school do not have this compost pit which serves as the end-destination of the biodegradable wastes. Currently, biodegradable wastes from the classrooms and offices are just thrown to the big blue bins to be retrieved by the municipal truck. These wastes are segregated from other types of wastes at the biggest material recovery facility in town which is located at Brgy. Bagumbayan Hilongos, Leyte.

Limited time allocation for zero-plastic project activities ranks second. The Department of Education has a lot of activities for the stakeholders resulting to the unsuccessful carrying-out of the zero-plastic projects initiated by YES-O. Teachers, who belong to internal stakeholders are bombarded with paper works and other tasks that prohibited them to join the activities which could be of great help to the school and the community as a whole. Notably, every project comes with limitations and risks. Project constraints define the limits of what the project team can do or have, and these constraints generally fall under scope, cost, and time. Some project managers consider time constraint as the most important among the project management constraints thus affects the implementation of a certain project/program as affirmed by Delos Santos (2022).

Conflict of schedule between important task and zero-plastic project activities is really true especially for the working parents, the valued external stakeholders of the school. Same is true with the Brgy. officials who also have duties and responsibilities in their beloved barangay. Even if how much they would love to join, the schedules do not permit and prohibit these stakeholders to participate. Udoagwu (2021) believes that a scheduling conflict in the workplace is when you have two tasks or events vying for your time and attention simultaneously. It is also a situation in which a team member is assigned two tasks or double shifts at the same time. Everyone faces schedule conflicts at work at some point. They may be caused by tight deadlines on a new project or an error in schedule plans. Schedule conflicts are disruptive and annoying and can result in total project failure or the delivery of subpar work. It is crucial to set up good workflow management and internal systems to minimize their occurrence or deal with them as they crop up. Regardless of how it occurs, a work schedule conflict demands that one person be in two places at once, which is not possible. This calls for a change to the schedule or an extra hand to help with the tasks or events.

CONCLUSION

Zero-plastic projects' successful implementation can have an array of factors, whether behavior, attitude, subjective norm or perceived behavioral control based on the Theory of Planned Behavior of Icek Ajzen (1985), as to which this study is anchored.

In this study, a total of 267 stakeholders of the school served as the respondents. These included the students, teachers and administrators as the internal stakeholders and the parents and brgy. officials as the external stakeholders. Regarding the awareness level of the stakeholders, the average number of responses is 188 which is equivalent to 71% of the whole respondents which showed that stakeholders were moderately aware of the existing zero-plastic projects.

Furthermore, as to the level of involvement, the over-all weighted mean was 3.95 which showed a high level of involvement among stakeholders. In addition, the zero-plastic projects mandated by Youth for Environment in Schools Organization (YES-O) were implemented in the school level with an overall weighted mean of 4.13 out of 5.

Upon getting the significant relationship among the stakeholders' level of awareness, implementation, and involvement on zero-plastic projects, chi-square and correlation were used. The result showed that the level of awareness and involvement of the stakeholders of Hilongos National Vocational School directly affect how it is implemented having a probability level or p-value $.006 < .01$ and $.000 < .01$ respectively which means it is significant. The results imply that the more aware and involve the stakeholders are, the more they implement the zero plastic projects.

Insufficient funds to purchase materials needed, limited time allocation and conflict of schedule between important task and zero-plastic activities were the problems faced by the stakeholders in implementing the zero-plastic projects. An income-generating sustainable intervention program is proposed.

It was recommended to reorient the zero-plastic projects to the different stakeholders and make it an annual activity. Science teachers and class advisers should always incorporate the zero-plastic projects in their classes and homeroom meetings to increase the level of awareness of stakeholders from moderately aware to extremely aware. Concepts on zero-plastic projects must be integrated in the school's monthly activities such as Nutrition Month, Science Month etc. The eco-friendly corner of the bulletin boards must be updated with the zero-plastic project mandates.

Next, establish a stakeholder's organization which will plan, lead and assess activities related to zero-plastics to improve the level of involvement from involved to extremely involved. Administrators, faculty and staff shall serve as role models to students, parents and brgy. officials in adopting the zero-plastic projects.

Then, monitor the ongoing project to maintain its high level of implementation. Provide a checklist for every classroom and offices to be used by the YES-O Officers in the weekly checking.

Furthermore, the school should foster partnerships with external stakeholders such as the Local Government Unit (LGU), Non-Government Organizations (NGO), private individuals and alumni to address scarcity of funds to purchase materials needed for zero-plastic projects.

Also, implement an income-generating project for the purchase of tumblers for the unfortunate students, establishment of a compost pit and repair of the Material Recovery Facility (MRF).

In addition, suggest further research focusing on strengthening and sustaining the existing zero-plastic projects.

Lastly, adopt the designed sustainable program on school's zero-plastic projects.

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